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Project-process approach as a tool for organizations striving for sustainable development and competitiveness in the market

KEYWORDS

project-process approach;
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 evaluation of project-process
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance is related to enterprises' adaptation to rapidly changing external environment conditions, increasing financial and economic stability, cost optimization, and improving the quality of products and services. The project-process approach allows us to respond to changes and implement innovations more effectively.

The article aims to theoretically justify the implementation of the project-process approach at the enterprise.

Materials and methods. The materials included articles from periodicals and books devoted to project management and production. System analysis and modeling methods were used.

Results of the study. The authors presented the organization's project-process management model and its implementation algorithm.

Indicators reflecting the cost of production, the overall level of costs, individual items at the enterprise as a whole, per unit of production, their dynamics, relative change, etc., can form the basis of the system for assessing the effectiveness of introducing and implementing the project-process approach to organizational management.

Conclusion. The project-process approach allows organizations to respond more flexibly to changes in market conditions and customer requirements. It facilitates quick adaptation to new technologies, products, and processes. The approach can become a significant tool for increasing enterprises' competitiveness and success.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the present research is due to the high level of competition in the market, the need for enterprises to adapt to rapidly changing conditions of the external environment, the need to increase financial and economic sustainability through implementation of internal reserves, the potential of the company, cost optimization, and improving the quality of products and services. The project-process approach to organizational management meets these requirements.

The project-process approach allows for a more effective response to changes and innovation introduction. Focusing on processes and projects helps identify bottlenecks and optimize work processes, which, in turn, leads to improved quality of products and services.

The project approach allows for better risk management associated with new initiatives, as each project has clearly defined objectives, timelines, and resources. It is also results-oriented, allowing organizations to assess their performance more clearly and achieve strategic goals.

A project-oriented structure promotes employees' more active involvement in the process, which increases their motivation and job satisfaction.

Thus, the project-process approach becomes an essential tool for organizations seeking sustainable development and competitiveness in the market.

Literature review

Managing processes in an enterprise is about optimizing them to reduce costs and increase productivity; it is also about making them flexible, clear, and innovative.

L. Brzezinski writes that enterprise development is not just growth or expansion but a comprehensive transformation that expands a company's capabilities and market presence. This development is driven by deliberate and systematic efforts to improve performance in all areas of business activity, aligned with stakeholder aspirations and organizational goals [1].

A. Kosieradzka and K. Rostek show that a single approach to process management (which does not consider the specificity of the organization's goals) is ineffective; process management should consider the organization's individuality. The authors highlight the differences between business process and process management, as well as the main success factors and limitations relevant to implementing process management in manufacturing companies and administrative agencies, respectively [2].

O. Arefieva et al. proposed a mechanism for managing the processes to ensure the enterprise's competitiveness in terms of informatization of economic processes. This mechanism allows us to determine the level of resource potential and better choose the optimal competitive strategy for the development of the enterprise. Decision-making will allow us to more accurately justify specific measures to strengthen market positions [3].

C. Wang et al. found that the three problems in China's current public procurement policy are, namely: 1) regulation of whole-process performance management needs to be optimized, 2) regulation of high-level performance management needs to be strengthened, and 3) regulation of whole process performance disclosure needs to be improved [4].

A. M. Ubaid and F. T. Dweiri write that business process management (BPM) is an effective performance management methodology for managing process-oriented organizations. The authors proposed a comprehensive BPM methodology that combines the steps of standard BPM and BPMS methodologies and the terminologies used in the reviewed methodologies [5].

I. Naugolnova substantiates the possibility of applying the process approach to cost management at project-oriented enterprises of engine building. This approach allows the distribution of direct and indirect costs per unit of production; it will enable to correctly justify its cost and market price to optimize the value chain, exclude unnecessary time and other resources, and increase the qualitative and quantitative indicators of products manufactured by engine building enterprises [6].

The project approach clearly defines goals and objectives, which helps achieve results more efficiently; it optimizes costs and promotes cooperation between different departments.

B. Arturo-Delgado and F. N. Dhaz-Piraquive present a review of studies conducted on applying project management processes in small and medium-sized enterprises worldwide to clarify the current status and provide recommendations to improve the management level in these organizations [7].

A. RezaHoseini writes that the results and consequences of selected projects have short-term and long-term effects on social, economic, and environmental conditions. Sustainable development involves considering both financial and non-financial factors [8].

P. Korenyuk et al. substantiated the necessity of using methodological approaches and tools for classifying investment projects, ranking them, and evaluating their effectiveness based on research to solve the management problem. The algorithm developed by the authors for determining priority investment projects and assessing their effectiveness will contribute to the optimal use of investment resources, ensuring effective investment activity management at an industrial enterprise [9].

Let us consider specific examples of using the project-process approach in various industries.

According to M. Liu, most of the modeling methods developed so far do not consider the individual needs of the project-type production. The authors present a unique method to model the crane lifting process in a shipyard [10].

Qy Li proposes an intelligent estimation method based on cloud computing technology. The authors prove that the intelligent evaluation method of assembly construction project management performance based on cloud computing technology is more accurate and timely in practical application and fully meets the requirements of the study [11].

M. Blomster & T. Koivumäki investigate organizational resources, competencies, and capabilities required to successfully implement machine learning development projects in digital marketing [12].

Few studies focus on integrating different approaches in organizational management.

A. Kühn writes about different philosophies and methodologies of project management, varying between the extremes of classical and agile project management. The authors highlight the advantages and disadvantages of successful project planning and execution in international business development [13].

U. Beister and M. Zeljkovic highlight the combination of traditional and agile project management. The authors believe hybrid project management is effective in certain situations [14].

A. Kosieradzka and K. Rostek write that manufacturing companies use Kaizen and Six Sigma concepts while the flexible approach is most common in public administration [15].

Based on the above, the scientific problem of implementing the project-process approach in production management is related to the need to form scientifically sound theories and models that clearly describe the relationship between project management and processes in the production environment.

The project-process approach involves a significant degree of uncertainty in project management. In this regard, scientific research on developing tools for risk assessment and prevention of negative consequences associated with the instability of the environment in which the enterprise operates is relevant.

Modern technologies play an essential role in ensuring the successful implementation of the project-process approach. Effective information systems that support interaction between projects and processes and provide access to data in real-time are necessary.

Thus, the scientific problem of implementing a project-process approach is insufficient theoretical basis, resistance to change, risk management, technology integration, and performance evaluation, which requires further research and development of solutions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Articles from academic journals on project management, industrial engineering, and production systems: 'International Journal of Agricultural Extension,' 'SN Business & Economics,' 'International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management, Environment, Development and Sustainability,' 'Social Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering,' 'Information Systems and e-Business Management,' etc. were used as materials for the article.

The study also used books on project management and processes in manufacturing containing descriptions of theories, methods, and practical cases.

System analysis methods were used to identify the relationships between projects and processes, and modeling was used to predict the consequences of implementing the new approach.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Project and process approaches to industrial enterprise management can be successfully combined. Allocation of separate projects at the enterprise and implementation of the process approach to project management within them reduces the labor intensity of the latter, increasing the accuracy of calculations of costs, profitability and other indicators of project efficiency.

Figure 1 shows the basic scheme of any process realization at the enterprise.

Figure 1 Basic scheme of process realization at the enterprise

When describing the project, we can generalize four main processes of its implementation:

- Project initiation, planning of estimated indicators, target benchmarks, etc...;
- Project realization, including management, monitoring, and control;
- Management change;
- Delivery of finished products, documentation, etc.

In this case, the model of the project-process approach to enterprise management takes the following form (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Model of project-process management of the organization (in Russian)

Figure 3 presents the algorithm of implementing project-process management of the organization

Figure 3 Algorithm of implementing the project-process approach to organization management (in Russian)

Implementing the project-process approach to organization management should start with the definition of the main activities, types of products, and services. If there are many such products, they should be grouped by similar characteristics or production processes. It is possible to single out only a few projects that bring a large share of revenue to the organization.

Depending on the number of allocated projects, complexity of the processes running in them, and their number and composition, organizational structure of the organization management is improved; the main project team is determined, within which the processes are allocated, their owners are appointed, and executors are appointed.

It is advisable to introduce the project-process approach to organizational management by first defining the main areas of activity, types of products manufactured, and services rendered. If such products are many, they should be grouped by similar characteristics or production processes. It is possible to single out only a few projects that bring a significant revenue share to the organization.

Depending on the number of allocated projects, complexity of the processes running in them, and their number and composition, organizational structure of the organization management is improved; the central project team is determined, within which the processes are allocated, their owners and executors are appointed.

It is advisable to use a method based on describing and optimizing the value chain and applying lean production principles as a tool for identifying and describing business processes within projects. This approach allows identifying losses at the operational level, eliminating unnecessary functions, and maximizing the reduction of business process costs.

Target indicators must be defined before implementing the project-process approach to managing an organization. Why does the company resort to such profound transformations of the usual organizational structure?

It is essential to determine which indicator will clearly show how practical the project-process approach to management is.

The main goal of any commercial organization is to make a profit. The basic model of the market changed; in the '50s and 60's, the basis of business was the ratio:

Costs of production + Desired value of profit = Cost of product realization.

The period 1970s-1990s saw a transformation of the market model, which the following relationship can now represent:

Cost of product realization – Cost of production = Profit.

That is, profit is the final result, the value of which is influenced by an external factor – the price that the consumer is willing to pay for the product, taking into account its qualitative characteristics and alternative offers on the market, and a factor that the enterprise can influence – the cost of production.

It is the level and the size of production costs at the enterprise that currently determine their competitiveness in the market. Therefore, the leading indicator that should be constantly monitored and reduced is the costs. Moreover, it is practically the only economic indicator to be evaluated for each project and process (subprocess, operation, function).

According to the author, indicators reflecting production cost, the overall level of costs, individual items at the enterprise as a whole, per unit of production, their dynamics, relative change, etc., can form the basis of the system for assessing the effectiveness of introducing and implementing the project-process approach to organizational management.

Monitoring the selected target indicators of project-process management efficiency allows developing measures to optimize project-process activity.

Certainly, other indicators are applicable and necessary to assess each process (subprocess, operation, function) performance. Cost-level control in process management is not the only task.

The number of customers, sales volume, duration of production cycle or a separate process, delivery time [16], and relative indicators characterizing the effectiveness of process management, such as profitability, turnover, etc., are related indicators, which should be oriented at introduction and realization of process management.

Restructuring the organizational structure under the project-process management model should positively impact the main final indicators of the organization's activity. Modeling business processes based on building and optimizing the value chain is the main tool for achieving the minimum cost of processes and a competitive price level in the market.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As H. L. Dienel rightly points out, almost every human activity can be defined as a project and as a process. Each project and process has its own dynamics and rhythm, a “natural oscillation” that can be identified, picked up, utilized, and shaped by project and process management. According to the author, process management is characterized by its openness to the results and the complexity of the initial situation and development compared to project management which focuses on specific goals [17].

The project-process approach in production management has considerable promise and can benefit organizations. The project-process approach allows organizations to respond more flexibly to changes in market conditions and customer requirements. It facilitates rapid adaptation to new technologies, products and processes.

The combination of project and process management allows for integrating various functions and a comprehensive approach to problem-solving. The project and process

approach helps allocate resources more rationally, which is especially important in conditions of limited budgets. The project approach contributes to better risk management, allowing the assessment of possible problems in advance at the planning stage and reducing the probability of their occurrence. The project-process approach focuses on continuous process improvement and product quality improvement. Modern technologies like IoT, Big Data, and AI can effectively integrate into a project-process approach to enhance analytical capabilities and automate routine tasks.

To successfully implement the project-process approach, organizations must focus on overcoming organizational barriers, training employees, and changing the corporate culture. In view of the above, the project-process approach can become a significant tool for increasing enterprises' competitiveness and success.

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